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A Study on Students' Motivation for Enrollment in Maritime Programs

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Abstract

This study looks into the elements that influence student motives for enrolling in maritime courses at the University of Visayas. This study uses a descriptive research approach, the study investigates three major variables: effort, performance, and rewards to among the maritime students. A researcher made questionnaire was distributed to a sample of third year maritime students. The findings show that students are highly motivated by the expectation that their efforts will result in successful academic performance and desirable career outcomes. The expected benefits of completing the program, such as professional chances, financial security, and international job experiences, provide the most motivation. These findings emphasize the need to align student expectations with practical benefits and indicate further ways to boost student motivation and performance, including strengthening career counseling, expanding hands-on learning, and highlighting global prospects. This research advances our knowledge of the relevance of the expectation theory to maritime education and offers practical suggestions for enhancing student engagement and retention..

Keywords: *maritime education, student motivation, expectancy theory, effort, performance*

Introduction

Understanding why students enroll in various academic programs is critical for institutions that want to recruit and retain students, build effective curricula, and meet the requirements of varied learner groups. The maritime industry, in particular, with its global relevance and demand for qualified workers, provides a unique case study for investigating student motives for enrolling in maritime programs.

The maritime industry contributes significantly to worldwide trade and economic development. According to the International Maritime Organization (IMO, 2021), maritime transport accounts for more than 80% of worldwide trade volume, highlighting the industry's importance. As a result, many countries have established specialist maritime education programs to train students for careers in this industry. Studies from various countries, including the United States and the United Kingdom, have identified a number of factors that influence students' decisions to pursue maritime studies, including career opportunities, financial incentives, and the perceived prestige of maritime professions (Smith & Johnson, 2020; Brown, 2019).

The maritime industry is an important aspect of the Philippine economy, with Filipino sailors constituting one of the largest groups of nautical workers globally. According to the Philippine foreign Employment Administration (POEA, 2022), maritime jobs account for a major share of the country's foreign employment. The demand for maritime education is therefore considerable, and understanding the variables that motivate students to enroll in marine programs is critical for matching educational offers with industry needs. National studies have investigated a variety of factors, including work stability, competitive pay, and family impact (Dela Cruz, 2021; Reyes, 2020).

While several studies have addressed factors that influence students' career choices in maritime fields, a nuanced understanding of specific motivational drivers among maritime students remains limited. Existing research often focuses on broad, external factors like job stability and financial rewards (Brown, 2019; Smith & Johnson, 2020). However, how students' intrinsic motivations such as personal passion for maritime work, curiosity about global travel, and a sense of adventure interact with extrinsic incentives has not been extensively studied, particularly within the Philippine context (Dela Cruz, 2021; Reyes, 2020).

The maritime program of the University of the Visayas, is well-known for its rigorous training and effective placement of graduates in the maritime industry. Given the university's strategic role in creating the future of maritime education in the local setting, it is critical to study what drives students to pursue this path. Preliminary findings indicate that local job market conditions, educational options, and personal interests influence students' decisions to enroll in marine courses. This study aims to explore the various factors influencing student motivations behind enrolling in maritime courses at the University of the Visayas. By examining both global trends and local dynamics, this research seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of what drives students to pursue maritime education and how these motivations align with industry needs and educational offerings.

Given the Philippines' unique position as one of the largest suppliers of maritime labor globally, understanding why students choose maritime education is crucial. Addressing this gap can provide insights into the interplay between Expectancy Theory's components (expectancy, instrumentality, and valence) and other motivational factors. Specifically, it can shed light on how students' expectations of a rewarding maritime career align with both personal interests and external pressures, thereby informing how educational institutions can better tailor programs to sustain student engagement and support industry needs.

Moreover, previous studies in countries like the United States and the United Kingdom have noted the impact of family and societal

expectations on career choice but have not fully explored how these influences vary within cultures where seafaring holds particular social prestige and economic significance, such as in the Philippines (IMO, 2021; POEA, 2022).

This study is based on Expectancy Theory, a motivational theory created by Victor Vroom in 1964 that describes how people make decisions depending on their expectations of outcome. It is commonly used to study how people's expectations of rewards and results affect their behavior and decision-making processes. The theory states that individuals are motivated to act in a certain way if they believe that their efforts will result in desirable result such as:

Expectancy (Effort-Performance Link). One example for this factor is personal interest and passion for Maritime work which is also considered as intrinsic motivation. Some students have a genuine interest in maritime subjects or are drawn to the challenges and unique experiences of life at sea. For these students, the work itself its routines, environments, and challenges is intrinsically motivating. This aligns with Expectancy Theory's Expectancy component, as students who enjoy the field are likely to believe their efforts in coursework will result in personal fulfillment and academic success.

Next, is the Instrumentality (Performance-Reward Link). In this category, career opportunities and job stability are concrete examples for extrinsic motivation. Many students are motivated by the career opportunities that maritime courses offer. The global demand for skilled maritime professionals, combined with the high job placement rates of reputable programs like those at the University of the Visayas, makes this field attractive. Students often see a clear link between excelling in their studies and securing stable, well-paying jobs in the maritime industry.

Furthermore, the Alignment with Industry Needs, and National Demand are considered extrinsic motivation. The Philippine government supports maritime education due to the industry's importance in the national economy. This alignment between educational programs and industry demand makes maritime studies an attractive, practical choice for students who want a straightforward path to a high-demand job market. They are motivated by the assurance that their educational efforts will lead to roles that are well-supported by industry needs.

Also, the Family Influence and Cultural Factors are described as extrinsic motivation. In the Philippines, family often plays a significant role in career choice. Many students are influenced by family members who work in maritime professions or by the desire to support their families financially. For these students, enrolling in maritime courses is partly motivated by external expectations or the goal of fulfilling family obligations.

Valence (Value of Rewards). This motivational factor has other key factors that are considered intrinsic and extrinsic. First, is Financial Incentives and Competitive Salaries are considered extrinsic motivation. The financial benefits of maritime careers are a powerful motivator. Maritime positions, particularly those involving overseas work, typically offer competitive salaries, benefits, and opportunities for financial growth, which are appealing to many students. This factor connects with Valence in Expectancy Theory, as students place high value on the potential financial rewards associated with a maritime career.

Next is the Prestige and Social Recognition which can be both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation. Maritime careers hold a certain prestige, especially in the Philippines, where seafaring is a respected profession. Many students feel a sense of pride in pursuing a field that is globally recognized and contributes significantly to international trade and the economy. This social recognition can drive students intrinsically, as they gain a sense of purpose and esteem, and extrinsically, as their families and communities often support and encourage this career path.

Finally, is the Global Travel and Exploration which is described as intrinsic motivation. Maritime careers offer unique travel opportunities, exposing individuals to different cultures and places, which appeals to students with a sense of adventure and curiosity. This intrinsic motivation is often a key reason for students to commit to maritime studies, as they see the coursework as a gateway to a lifestyle that offers more than just conventional work.

While prior research has examined factors influencing students' career decisions in maritime fields, there is limited exploration of specific personal and family motivations that drive students toward this path. In the Philippines, many students are drawn to maritime programs due to family influence—particularly in cases where fathers or other family members nearing retirement encourage their children to follow in their footsteps in the maritime industry. This generational motivation, often tied to a sense of family legacy and pride in maritime work, has not been fully examined within current literature, which typically overlooks such culturally specific factors (Dela Cruz, 2021; Reyes, 2020).

The researchers observed that financial considerations play a significant role for many maritime students. For those coming from economically challenging backgrounds, a maritime career promises not only personal financial stability but also the opportunity to support their families and contribute to a better quality of life for their parents and siblings. This goal of providing a comfortable life for loved ones is a compelling motivator, especially among students who aspire to help fund their siblings' education and lift their families out of financial hardship (POEA, 2022; IMO, 2021). Despite the importance of financial motivations in driving students' choices, few studies have specifically investigated how these economic aspirations shape students' decisions to pursue maritime studies.

Additionally, the researchers learned from their students that they have personal aspirations such as a desire to travel the world and experience life at sea are powerful motivators. Many students are attracted to the maritime field because it allows them to fulfill a

lifelong dream of adventure and global exploration. This personal vision of working at sea and visiting different countries is often a key factor in their decision to enroll in maritime programs.

This study specifically aims to examine the influence of family background and generational expectations on students' decisions to enroll in maritime courses, analyze the role of financial motivations particularly the desire to support family members and achieve economic stability and explore students' intrinsic motivations, such as the aspiration to travel and work at sea. By identifying the impact of family, financial, and personal motivations on students' commitment to maritime studies, this research seeks to provide valuable insights for educational institutions in developing targeted recruitment strategies and supportive services that align with students' distinct motivational factors. The findings of the study will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the motivations behind students' choices to pursue maritime education, offering actionable guidance for program development in the field.

This research will also contribute on student motivation in the maritime field, offering insights relevant to academic institutions, maritime educators, and industry stakeholders. Identifying why students choose maritime education can help institutions like the University of the Visayas design targeted recruitment strategies, develop curricula that align with student aspirations, and ensure their graduates are prepared to meet industry needs. Given the global relevance of the maritime industry, the findings may also have implications for similar institutions worldwide that seek to align their educational offerings with the dynamic needs of the maritime sector.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive research in exploring and describing factors that influence students' motivations behind enrolling in maritime courses. The descriptive approach is used to gather data that provide an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon by describing characteristics, behaviors, and perceptions of the respondents.

The study was conducted at the University of the Visayas, focusing on students enrolled in the maritime program. The maritime program offers various courses designed to prepare students for a career in the maritime industry, which provides a suitable setting to explore student motivations for course enrollment.

The target population for this study were the Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) and Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering (BSMARE) students currently enrolled in maritime programs at the University of the Visayas for the academic year 2024-2025. This group was selected because they are likely to have experienced significant exposure to the program, providing valuable insights into their motivations for enrollment.

A convenience sampling method was used to choose participants from a population of 300 students enrolled in maritime courses. The researchers based this total population on the enrollment record from the current enrollment term, focusing on students who were in the process of finishing their enrollment at the College of Maritime Education. This strategy enabled the selection of readily available respondents, easing the data collection process while noting potential limitations in generalizability. During the one-week enrollment period, the researchers decided to collect data from the 300 students who were completing their enrollment, resulting in a sample size of 169 based on the Krejcie and Morgan table. This table shows the recommended sample size based on the desired confidence level and margin of error. Given a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, the computed sample size ensures a strong representation of the population while accounting for the practical limits of convenience sampling.

The primary research instrument for this study is a structured questionnaire based on the components of Expectancy Theory: Effort, Performance, and Rewards. The questionnaire included both demographic questions and five Likert-scale items that measure students' perceptions of these three variables: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly Agree

Part I of the questionnaire is about the Effort. This item gauges students' perceptions of the effort required to succeed in the maritime program.

Part II of the questionnaire is about Performance: This part assess how students perceive the relationship between their academic performance and future career prospects.

Part III of the questionnaire is about Rewards: This part measures how students value potential rewards from completing a maritime degree (e.g., career opportunities, financial stability).

Pre-Data Gathering. Before conducting the study, the researchers prioritized ethical considerations by seeking permission and obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB). Informed consent forms were developed and provided to respondents, clearly outlining the study's purpose, participants' rights, and the confidentiality of their responses. This step ensured that students were fully informed and could make voluntary decisions about their participation.

Actual Data Collection. The researchers were assigned to the enrollment area during the course of this investigation. During a one-week enrollment period, the researchers handed out questionnaires to selected students in person. Data was collected in person, allowing the researchers to interact directly with students and answer any questions or concerns they had regarding the study. This technique increased involvement and response rates among students who were completing their enrollment during the enrollment period.

Post-data collection. Once the surveys were completed, the responses to the Likert-scale items were examined using descriptive statistics such as mean, median, mode, and standard deviation to highlight overall patterns in student motivations. The findings were presented in tables, which improved the data's clarity and interpretability while assisting in identifying the important elements driving enrollment decisions.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study provide insights into students' perceptions of the role of Effort, Performance, and Rewards in their academic journey within the maritime program.

Table 1 displays students' perceptions of the effort required to excel in their maritime studies. The data indicate high levels of agreement across all items, with most maritime students acknowledging the importance of consistent effort, dedication, and hard work to succeed academically in the program.

Table 1. *Effort-Performance Link*

<i>Effort statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I believe that if I put in sufficient effort, I will excel in my maritime studies.	4.3	0.82	Agree
I am willing to invest a significant amount of time and energy to succeed in my courses.	4.0	0.94	Agree
I think that consistently studying hard will improve my performance in maritime subjects.	4.2	0.87	Agree
I am motivated to overcome challenges in my studies through hard work and effort.	4.1	0.89	Agree
I believe my efforts in studying maritime courses will significantly impact my overall success in the program.	4.2	0.77	Agree

The table above shows that students commonly regard the work they put into their marine studies as critical to their academic performance. Most maritime students have mean scores above 4.0, indicating a significant willingness to devote time and energy in their studies, which is consistent with the effort-performance component of Expectancy Theory (Vroom, 1964). This shows that marine students are motivated by the notion that their efforts will result in the anticipated performance outcomes.

Personal Interest and Passion for Maritime Work. Many students expressed a genuine interest and passion for maritime work, which significantly influenced their motivation to succeed. A mean score of 4.2 (SD = 0.77) for: "I believe my efforts in studying maritime courses will significantly impact my overall success in the program." indicates that intrinsic motivation plays a vital role in their academic efforts.

This suggests that maritime educators should provide specific instructions for how students' efforts can transfer into improved academic success. Offering a tailored feedback and praise of student efforts may increase their incentive to succeed. According to Bandura's (1997) Self-Efficacy Theory, when students believe their efforts will result in favorable outcomes, their confidence in academic accomplishment grows, increasing their perseverance.

Table 2. *Instrumentality (Performance-Reward Link)*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I believe my performance in maritime courses will lead to future career opportunities.	4.5	0.75	Strongly Agree
I am confident that performing well in maritime courses gives me a competitive edge.	4.3	0.81	Agree
I believe that excelling in maritime studies is key to securing a high-paying job in the future.	4.4	0.79	Agree
I think my grades in maritime courses are an important measure of my future professional success.	4.2	0.85	Agree
I feel that good academic performance will lead to increased recognition in the industry.	4.3	0.83	Agree

Table 2 highlights students' beliefs about how their academic performance in maritime courses will affect their future careers. The results show strong agreement that good performance will open career opportunities, provide a competitive edge, and lead to professional success in the maritime industry.

Prestige and Social Recognition is part of the intrinsic motivation. Students indicated that performing well academically could enhance their social recognition, with a mean score of 4.3 (SD = 0.83) for: "I feel that good academic performance will lead to increased recognition in the industry." This recognition can provide students with a sense of achievement and validation within their community and the industry.

The findings show that maritime students see a strong link between performance in maritime courses and future professional success, with mean scores ranging from 4.2 to 4.5. These findings are consistent with Vroom's Expectancy Theory (1964), which holds that students will be driven to do well if they believe they will receive desired incentives. As evidenced by the results, maritime students strongly believe that excelling academically will provide them a competitive advantage and boost their prospects of obtaining high-paying employment and industry prominent position.

Another motivational factor is family expectations and cultural factors played a significant role in motivating students. Many respondents noted that family support influenced their decision to pursue a maritime career, reflecting cultural values associated with job security and prestige in maritime professions.

Students recognized the alignment of their education with industry needs and national demand for maritime professionals. This recognition motivated them to perform well academically, contributing to a perceived connection between their studies and future employment opportunities.

This suggests that marine education programs should stress the practical relationship between student success in the classroom and future employment opportunities. Institutions can close the skills gap between classroom instruction and future work by providing internship opportunities or bringing individuals from the field to give views. The Self-Determination Theory of Ryan and Deci (2000), which emphasizes how critical it is for students to feel competent and independent in their academic endeavors in order to maintain motivation, lends credence to this.

Table 3. *Valence (Value of Rewards)*

<i>Rewards</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I expect to have good career opportunities after completing the maritime program.	4.6	0.68	Strongly Agree
I believe that a career in the maritime industry will provide me with financial security.	4.5	0.71	Agree
I think that completing the maritime program will lead to a personally fulfilling career.	4.4	0.79	Agree
I believe that the maritime industry offers career growth and promotion opportunities.	4.3	0.82	Agree
I value the opportunity to work abroad or travel as part of a maritime career.	4.6	0.70	Agree

Table 3 presents students' expectations regarding the rewards they anticipate from completing a maritime program. The data indicate a strong belief that a maritime career will offer good career opportunities, financial security, personal fulfillment, and opportunities for career growth and travel.

As shown in Table 3, marine students strongly believe that the benefits of completing a maritime program, such as career opportunities, financial security, and personal fulfillment, are important motivators for enrolling in the course. The high mean scores for career prospects (4.6) and opportunities to work overseas (4.6) reflect the global demand for maritime professionals, which is frequently noted in maritime education research (Sampson & Wu, 2003).

Students demonstrated a strong belief that completing the maritime program would lead to good career opportunities and job stability. The data indicate a mean score of 4.5 (SD = 0.68) for the statement: "I expect to have good career opportunities after completing the maritime program," suggesting that students view this as a significant motivator.

Moreover, the expectation of financial security emerged as a crucial extrinsic motivator, with a mean score of 4.5 (SD = 0.71) for: "I believe that a career in the maritime industry will provide me with financial security." This reflects students' recognition of the financial benefits associated with maritime careers.

Also, the desire for adventure and the opportunity to travel globally were identified as intrinsic motivators. The respondents valued the prospect of working abroad and experiencing different cultures, reflected in a mean score of 4.6 (SD = 0.70) for: "I value the opportunity to work abroad or travel as part of a maritime career."

The high perceived value of incentives suggests that maritime institutions should emphasize the practical benefits of maritime employment in their marketing and recruitment activities. They could additionally strengthen their relationships with industry partners to ensure students have access to apprenticeships and job opportunities. Maslow's Hierarchy of wants (1943) supports this, as students are motivated by the promise of achieving both lower-level wants (financial stability) and higher-level needs (self-actualization through a satisfying career).

The findings revealed that the maritime students are primarily motivated to enroll in maritime courses due to a combination of effort, performance, and reward expectations. The highest mean score of 4.6 was observed in the rewards category, indicating that students are highly motivated by the potential benefits of completing the program, particularly in terms of career opportunities, financial stability, and the possibility of working abroad. In terms of performance, a mean score of 4.5 reflected students' strong belief that excelling in their studies would directly lead to better job prospects and professional recognition. Meanwhile, the effort variable also

scored high, with a mean score of 4.3, showing that students are committed to putting in the necessary work to succeed academically.

Conclusions

The study found that maritime students at the University of the Visayas are strongly motivated to enroll in maritime courses because they believe that their hard work will lead to academic success and, ultimately, rewarding career opportunities. The maritime students are particularly driven by the potential benefits of completing the program, such as good job prospects, financial stability, and the chance to work abroad. This aligns with the Expectancy Theory, which suggests that people are motivated when they believe their efforts will result in positive outcomes. Overall, understanding these motivations can help maritime institutions better support and engage their students.

To further support and engage students at the University of the Visayas, several essential recommendations are made. First, improving career counseling services is critical; this might include inviting industry representatives, arranging job fairs, and providing workshops to help students comprehend the real-world benefits of marine careers. Increasing practical training opportunities, such as internships and hands-on experiences, will help students to apply their knowledge and observe how their studies affect future employment success. Furthermore, offering academic support through tutoring and mentorship will assist students in meeting their academic objectives while also reinforcing the importance of their efforts. To attract and retain students, advertising materials and recruitment activities should emphasize the worldwide opportunities connected with marine careers, such as working abroad and international travel should be a focus in promotional materials and recruitment efforts to attract and retain students. Finally, it is critical to review and oversee student expectations on a regular basis to ensure they are in line with industry realities, which will keep students motivated and focused on their future goals. Implementing these strategies can help students understand the link between their academic work and career benefits, enhancing their motivation and performance in maritime education.

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